

Challenges and opportunities of public space management in Mexico

Sergio Alvarado Vazquez^{a,*}, Ana Mafalda Madureira^b, Frank O. Ostermann^c, Karin Pfeffer^b

^a Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation, Hengelosestraat 99, 7514 AE Enschede, the Netherlands

^b Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation, Hengelosestraat 99, Department of Urban and Regional Planning and Geo-Information Management, Enschede 7514 AE, the Netherlands

^c Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation, Hengelosestraat 99, Department of Geo-information Processing, Enschede 7514 AE, the Netherlands

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the opportunities and challenges of public space management (PSM) in the Mexican context by analysing the perspectives of different governance actors. Issues in the PSM literature include ineffective political decisions, prevalence of the private sector, lack of coordination between government institutions, and a need for more effective social participation. While most PSM studies focus on European cities, empirical PSM knowledge in the Latin American context is scarce. To address this gap, this research elucidates the Mexican context by investigating and adapting a PSM framework in Mexico City and Puebla. The case study research is based on qualitative document research and interview analysis from four groups of governance actors: government officials, academics, NGOs, and architecture/urban planning firms. We found multiple PSM challenges: uncoordinated efforts in the maintenance of public space, lack of and polarisation of investment, and privatisation of public space. At the intra-governmental level, the research identified a lack of coordination between government institutions, increasing reliance on the private sector, and limited opportunities for residents to participate in PSM processes. The paper highlights missing links between existing governance actors involved in PSM and wider residents, in the pursuit of the ambitious role of achieving public space quality.

1. Introduction

Public space management (PSM) is an approach for the planning, design and maintenance of public spaces and concerns how planned and existing public spaces are regulated, how the facilities are provided, and their quality, design, and management (Carmona et al., 2008; Praliya & Garg, 2019). PSM aims to tackle the main challenges in public space development, namely the regulation, coordination, investment, and maintenance of efforts among involved actors and institutions. Policy-makers and scholars highlight the importance of PSM as a key element for creating social, safe, and healthy public spaces. Well-planned, well-designed and well-maintained public spaces provide social, economic and environmental resources that enhance the liveability of cities (Carmona et al., 2008; Kher Kaw et al., 2020). However, some actors involved in the planning, design and maintenance of public spaces (i.e., government actors and local communities) perceive a decline in how they are managed. For example, many public spaces present adverse conditions, poor design, and are perceived as insecure by the communities where they are located (Carmona & De Magalhaes, 2006;

Hernández Bonilla, 2012; Páramo et al., 2018).

Recently, PSM has gained more attention across the world. Several organisations (e.g., the World Bank, the Inter-American Development Bank) have developed programs and strategies explicitly targeting the improvement of public spaces, bringing into the spotlight the importance of public spaces and how to manage them effectively (Finger & Barnett, 2019; Kher Kaw et al., 2020). Public spaces were integrated into the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), specifically Target 11.7 on providing universal access to safe, inclusive, and accessible green public spaces to everyone by 2030 (United Nations, 2015). A study in the Dutch context shows the existing gap in academia regarding PSM in practice, the need for approaches that avoid the ineffectiveness of PSM, policy changes to emphasise PSM importance, and the need for new forms of stakeholder involvement (Duivenvoorden et al., 2021).

However, the implementation of PSM in practice faces diverse challenges. The first challenge is that political decisions and institutional interests seem to favour the perspective of the private sector, due to expected economic contributions despite local government ambitions to involve a more diverse group of governance actors in PSM (Auerbach,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: s.alvaradovazquez@utwente.nl (S. Alvarado Vazquez), m.madureira@utwente.nl (A.M. Madureira), f.o.ostermann@utwente.nl (F.O. Ostermann), k.pfeffer@utwente.nl (K. Pfeffer).

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2012; Delgadillo, 2018; Low, 2005). As a consequence, some urban projects are carried out because of political campaign promises or interests and are not based on coherent urban plans or policy debates (Koops & Galič, 2017; Zamanifard et al., 2018). Recent studies revealed that private sector actors develop sophisticated systems for privatised PSM through public–private partnerships with government institutions, as seen in Copenhagen (Carmona et al., 2019). In these arrangements, PSM favours the economic interests of these actors, at the expense of social or environmental concerns, neglecting the interests and needs of the users of the public space (Delgadillo, 2018).

The second challenge concerns the lack of organisation and coordination between government institutions involved in the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces. According to De Magalhães and Carmona (2006), PSM should consider different actors and government institutions in a coordinated and organised way throughout all project stages, from conceptual design to aftercare and maintenance. However, the lack of internal coordination between governmental institutions and external coordination with other stakeholders has generated under-management on the physical conditions of public spaces; external factors such as economic, political, planning policy debates and ideological differences have also affected decision-making on planned and existing public spaces (De Magalhães & Carmona, 2006; Zamanifard et al., 2018). The result is an absence of leadership in assuming responsibilities and follow-up, with deteriorating public space conditions in less-favoured areas of the city (Alessandri Carlos, 2018).

The third challenge is the lack of opportunities for residents to participate in the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces. Traditionally, this task was the sole responsibility of public institutions, with social actors usually only being informed, or at best consulted, about decisions (Arnstein, 1969). Social actors have succeeded in carving out more spaces for direct involvement through socially organised initiatives, such as tactical urbanism or placemaking (Gehl & Svarre, 2013; Lydon et al., 2012); however, exclusionary practices still dominate and stifle the opinions of the users of these public spaces (Zamanifard et al., 2018).

Current PSM studies have mainly focused on European cities. Carmona's work on London, Copenhagen, and Oslo showcases PSM's problems of over-management (e.g., public–private partnerships promoting the commodification and homogenisation of the public space) and under-management (e.g., associated with poorly designed and insecure spaces) (Carmona et al., 2019). According to Chitrakar et al. (2022), the prevailing commodification practices in public space production are causing over-management, with excessive control exercised by non-governmental organisations or private entities (Chitrakar et al., 2022). Latin American cities are marked by a lack of public spaces in marginalized areas and under-management of the existing ones (Vergara et al., 2015), and the need to raise awareness and promote social knowledge on how public spaces are managed or where they should be developed involving social actors (Borja & Muxi, 2003).

Despite the relevance of PSM worldwide, there is a need for a deeper understanding of the potential of managing public spaces in non-European contexts (Chitrakar et al., 2022), including Latin America and the specific case of Mexico (Páramo et al., 2018; Ramírez Rosete et al., 2019). Also, only a few studies have been developed to understand PSM from the Mexican perspective.¹ Examples include the analysis of land management in Puebla with an implicit reference to public spaces (Gutiérrez Juárez et al., 2022; Ramírez Rosete et al., 2019), the development of a methodological model to manage green areas from the

¹ This was confirmed by a literature review that we conducted using the keywords “public”, “space”, “management”, and “Mexico” in the Scopus database in February 2023. We used ASReview to analyse the review results and identified 121 documents. Twenty papers were identified as relevant in the Scopus database, the analytics obtained through ASReview can be seen in the Appendix Fig. 13.

perspective of environmental preservation (Pena-Salmon & Rojas-Caldelas, 2009) or the investigation of well-being, quality of life, availability and habitability of public spaces (Ayala-azcárraga et al., 2019; Blancarte-Siqueiros et al., 2019; Gutiérrez et al., 2021). To fully understand the growing complexity of public space management at both local and international levels, additional research is needed within both academic and practical spheres (Chitrakar et al., 2022; Duivenvoorden et al., 2021; Páramo et al., 2018).

This paper discusses current challenges and opportunities of PSM in a Latin American context. We adapt an existing PSM framework developed for the European context (Carmona et al., 2008), and include a section on the context of public spaces and the dimension of social participation to better reflect the empirical context to which this framework is applied to, here - the Mexican context. The novelty of this research lies in its conceptual contribution and empirical application. It discusses the opportunities and challenges in the Mexican context, generating new insights on PSM in a non-European country. We used an explorative qualitative approach to analyse PSM in two case studies in the Mexico City Megalopolis: Mexico City and Puebla City, through the perspectives of different governance actors.

The cities were selected due to differences in size and their budget investments. They share similar challenges related to informality in public spaces. Additionally, the authors had prior knowledge of ongoing public spaces issues. The research employs a qualitative approach, drawing on document research, semi-structured interviews, and observations in the field. It illustrates how the PSM framework can be applied to the case of Mexico; what the current challenges are according to four groups of governance actors in the two cities; and how public spaces are currently managed in those cities.

This paper is divided into six sections. After the introduction, Section 2 discusses the concept of public space, PSM, and the governance actors. Section 3 provides the research methods with a brief outline of the case study context and the methods used to collect and analyse the data in Mexico. Section 4 describes the key findings on PSM dimensions. Section 5 discusses the adapted PSM framework brought from the European into the Latin American context, followed by Section 6, concluding with the scientific and social relevance on this research.

2. Public space, public space management, and governance actors

2.1. Public spaces and their importance for cities

Public spaces have been extensively researched as an essential component for social interactions in historical and contemporary cities in the fields of urban planning, design and urban studies (Li et al., 2022). They have been referred to as physical spaces that are accessible to diverse groups of people and are outside the boundary of private properties (Jacobs, 1961; Madanipour, 2015; Mandeli, 2019), where social life and interactions unfold, economic activities are developed, and traditions are reflected, producing vibrant cities but also socio-political expressions (Gehl, 2004; Harvey, 2000; Jacobs, 1961; Jakoubč, 2013). Duivenvoorden et al. (2021) define public spaces as a valuable asset to cities, offering public and private infrastructure, such as roads and parks, and enhancing social benefits and quality of life. In this sense, public spaces are communally shared areas, traditionally managed by the government in urban or rural areas, with different functional or symbolic purposes for local residents (Gehl & Svarre, 2013; Madanipour, 1999). UN-Habitat defines them as “all the places publicly owned or of public use, accessible and enjoyable by all for free and without a profit motive” (Garau, 2015, p. 6). They are a vital part of the urban infrastructure, promoting the collective life of residents (Madanipour, 1999). Public spaces should be inclusive, have minimal constraints on behaviour, encourage spontaneous activities, and foster social interaction (Li et al., 2022).

However, critical studies have noted a decline in the public space

worldwide, where the lack of management has led to littered, polluted and unsafe public spaces with poor design in unattended neighbourhoods (Carmona & De Magalhães, 2006; Hernández Bonilla, 2008). This is primarily due to challenges related to the lack of institutional coordination and evaluations for good management and the lack of policy instruments, which has brought public space degradation and undermanagement (Beqaj, 2016; Carmona, 2010b; Chitrakar et al., 2022). The decline of public spaces is also linked to inequality. Wealthy communities have private management, budget and philanthropic activities to collect resources and therefore usually have well-maintained public spaces (Kher Kaw et al., 2020; Ribeiro-Palacios et al., 2021). The opposite happens in low and middle-income areas, where the decline is evident in the physical conditions of their public space due to unaffordable maintenance costs by local governments or the residents (Hernández Bonilla, 2013; Nikšić & Sezer, 2017).

How public spaces are planned, designed and managed has a crucial impact on supporting social interactions, stimulating the activity in the space, and attracting different users to the cities (Carmona et al., 2010; Madanipour, 1999). Hence, public spaces are being planned, designed and (re)developed according to a new set of policy goals (e.g. public health, inclusion, climatic adaptation, circular economy) (Carmona, 2019; Duivenvoorden et al., 2021). Recent studies explore the link between urban planning, public spaces and well-being and how the future of cities will be the result of power relations among stakeholders to define the management of new public spaces worldwide (Chitrakar et al., 2022; Honey-Rosés et al., 2021; Kher Kaw et al., 2020). Furthermore, residents recognise the importance of protecting public spaces as cultural heritage (García, 2017). The recent work on public spaces thus emphasises the critical importance of aligning social functions and interactions with the political dimension of public space management, highlighting the valuable insights gained from local residents who utilise these spaces.

In line with these definitions and foci of recent research, this research understands public spaces as physical areas in a city where different social, cultural, artistic, recreational, political activities and functions unfold, and where social expressions and manifestations can be shared among local residents. We focus on public spaces located at the neighbourhood scale that support everyday activities within their immediate surroundings (Stanley et al., 2012), where its management is the responsibility of local government but which can be privately or publicly maintained, and that offer flexible functions and are appropriated by a community. Our definition was also inductively refined based on our interviewees' responses. For them, public spaces are parks, community gardens, urban remnants, streets, or the popular corner in the neighbourhood.

2.2. Importance of public space management

Studies stated that public space management became relevant when the decline of contemporary public spaces started to be more evident through the commodification and homogenisation of public spaces in Western cities (Carmona & De Magalhães, 2006; Jacobs, 1961; Praliya & Garg, 2019). To understand the complexity of PSM, various perspectives have been developed on how public spaces are defined and analysed, employing multiple dimensions (Li et al., 2022; Mandeli, 2010). A study from the accessibility perspective proposes the use of four dimensions based on how public spaces are accessed, how behaviour is sanctioned when used, and what their rules of use and access are (Li et al., 2022). One of the proposed frameworks by Carmona et al. (2008) analyses the character of public spaces based on three main aspects: what elements constitute a public space, their particular qualities, and appearance of the physical context. A study using the water management perspective proposed to consider the social, political and environmental dimensions in the design of public spaces (Ricart et al., 2022). Furthermore, for the management of public spaces in England, (De Magalhães & Carmona, 2009) propose four dimensions that seek to ensure public spaces

function correctly between those who manage them and those who use them; the framework is the same used by Carmona et al. (2008).

For this study, we draw on the PSM framework that Carmona et al. (2008) developed to analyse how public spaces are planned, designed, and maintained in the Mexican context. Carmona et al. (2008) define PSM as a set of processes and practices that shape the quality and plurality of public spaces through the aspirations and demands of different governance actors in a way that is acceptable to its users. The PSM framework is suitable due to its purpose of understanding the activities undertaken by different groups of stakeholders, their involvement and the transfer of responsibilities (Carmona et al., 2008). The governance of these spaces is organised around the interaction between central governing actors and social stakeholders (De Magalhães & Carmona, 2009). The PSM framework presented by Carmona et al. (2008) proposes four interconnected dimensions (Carmona et al., 2008, p. 68):

1. Regulations in public space policies;
2. Coordination of interventions;
3. Definition and deployment of maintenance routines;
4. Investment in public spaces and their services.

The model aims to tackle the decline of public spaces and spur on cleaner, safer, greener and healthier public spaces, by improving how they are planned, designed and maintained (Carmona et al., 2008). From the perspective of urban planning, the *regulation* dimension is the one focused on regulatory planning instruments, where public spaces can and need to be located, how they should be used and how they need to be adapted for future societal needs (De Magalhães & Carmona, 2009). The *coordination* dimension is focused on the actions of different actors whose actions will have an impact on public spaces such as the coordination of public sector services. The dimensions of *maintenance* and *investment* ensure the space can be used as intended, for example, by maintaining its functions, re-designing for future needs or its occasional replacement or removal. The dimensions will be explained in greater detail in the analytical framework in Section 3.

The application of the framework in different contexts (Chitrakar et al., 2022; Mandeli, 2010; Zamanifard et al., 2018) shows its reproducibility to contexts beyond its original context of application. Recognising the context of public spaces allows one to understand how they are envisioned, what stakeholders desire in an ideal public space, and how public spaces operate as they evolve over time and across geographical locations (Zamanifard et al., 2018). Defining what constitutes a public space enables identifying the functions, aspirations and meanings that stakeholders associate with these spaces and allows them to prioritise the arrangements needed to achieve quality in the public space (Li et al., 2022). The aspirations of residents and other stakeholders regarding public spaces can increase the empowerment of residents and other stakeholders interested in improving the conditions of their public spaces, specifically when improvements based on their needs are achieved, which varies based on the cultural, economic and social context (Hernández Bonilla, 2013). Lastly, comprehending the physical conditions, functions, and uses has been discussed as essential to understanding the context of public spaces (Mehta, 2014).

Carmona et al. (2008) present different models to understand public spaces, where context has different considerations. An example is the "dimensions of the public space character", where they consider a dimension called 'the context for action', referring to understanding a neighbourhood's socioeconomic situation in the European context. Later, they present the "open space management analytical framework", on which they consider a dimension called the "management context", referring to understanding the types of public spaces, stakeholders, needs, and policies through eleven innovative cities. However, Carmona et al. (2008) do not consider how the context in different geographical locations, particularly in emergent economies, might influence the meaning attached to what is a public space, what are the aspirations regarding the functions and role of these spaces, and what are the

current conditions and functions perceived by governance actors in the public space (Hernández Bonilla, 2013; Li et al., 2022; Mehta, 2014; Zamanifard et al., 2018).

Adopting the PSM framework to the Mexican case can highlight the importance of understanding the physical, functional, and socio-cultural context, the role of social participation, and the possibility of modifying the framework to fit the context. This is seen in the proposed public space governance framework by Zamanifard et al. (2018), who also considered some aspects of the PSM Framework of Carmona et al. (2008) and integrated four additional components regarding governance structure, tools, tasks and gave a major role to the consideration of actors and stakeholders. Social participation in the work of Carmona et al. (2008) is implicitly part of the coordination dimension. However, as stated in other studies related to the management of public space (Duivenvoorden et al., 2021; Mandeli, 2019; Paukaeva et al., 2021; Zamanifard et al., 2018), and particularly by researchers in the Mexican context (Duivenvoorden et al., 2021; Páramo et al., 2018; Ramírez Rosete et al., 2019), social participation is an important element that needs to be considered as a dimension on its own due to the relevance of understanding how social actors and other relevant stakeholders are engaged.

2.3. Governance and governance actors of PSM

From the perspective of urban policy, governance is defined as the coordinated action and resource allocation by different stakeholders to pursue collective objectives through different processes and mechanisms (Pierre, 2005). These aims are similar to what PSM seeks to achieve, according to Carmona et al. (2008) definition. On the differences between government and governance, Mandeli (2010, 2019) explains that government is an instrument that applies control, power, and management, while governance refers to the processes of using regulations, laws, and codes to shape the quality of the built environment for the public interest, including public spaces, hence our focus on governance actors.

The literature commonly identifies five groups of actors that influence policies and decision-making processes in urban planning and design (Gehl & Svarre, 2013; Mandeli, 2010): Government; Non-governmental organisations; Architecture/Urban planning firms; Academics; and Local residents.

- **Government:** Institutions and agencies at the federal, state, and municipal level that attend to specific aspects of public spaces. (Mandeli, 2010; United Cities and Local Governments, 2016).
- **Non-governmental organisations:** Mostly focused on the local context and usually formed by residents who share a common view on a specific problem (Borja, 2011; Madanipour, 1999). NGOs have been seen as representatives of local residents or defenders of the public interest in several theoretical research (Mohanty, 2002; Schoenefeld, 2021). For our research, we consider NGOs as representatives of residents and users, and hence representatives of a bottom-up view on participatory processes (Zamanifard et al., 2018).
- **Architecture/Urban planning firms:** They focus on planning and designing project proposals requested by the government, i.e., invitations to tender and win government contracts. Often, governments do not have the technical or operational capacity to develop project proposals and hire external consultancies (Cuenya, 2009). We do not consider real estate companies since their motivation is the financial investment in public properties for profit; for planning and design, they usually hire architecture/urban planning firms (Tiesdell & Adams, 2011).
- **Academia:** Local universities usually provide scientific knowledge about the local conditions and are invited to participate as consultants in a decision-making process as experts (Gehl & Svarre, 2013; Ziccardi, 2012).

- **Local residents:** Defined as the group of individuals living in formal or informal built environments who visit, live, appropriate and are aware of the benefits and challenges of the urban spaces in their vicinity (Ives et al., 2017; Lombard, 2014; Styliadis et al., 2016).

2.4. Current studies in PSM

Recent studies on PSM reflect the trend of local authorities actively involving different stakeholders in the production of long-term management of public spaces in the Global North, such as the United Kingdom, Denmark or Australia (Carmona et al., 2019; Zamanifard et al., 2018). In other geographical contexts such, as Nepal and Saudi Arabia, scholars have underscored the significance of engaging local residents in PSM as a strategy to enhance the quality of public spaces (Chitrakar et al., 2022; Mandeli, 2019). As indicated in the subsection before, the five stakeholder groups mentioned above are, in theory, actors that are influencing or have a say in policies and decision-making processes on PSM. Cities such as London, Copenhagen, or Oslo adopted New Public Management approaches, where public and private actors work together to achieve the joint goals of improving public spaces (Carmona et al., 2019; Zamanifard et al., 2018). This new type of management also reached Latin American cities such as Brasília, Buenos Aires or Mexico City, influenced by North American cities and international institutions (Delamaza, 2011; Hernández Bonilla, 2013).

Hence, countries with emerging economies are also putting emphasis on public space quality and its management in urban regeneration interventions, such as Mexico, Peru, India or Kenya (Kher Kaw et al., 2020; Páramo et al., 2018; Praliya & Garg, 2019). Some researchers argue that current PSM challenges are related to weak urban governance at the neighbourhood level, the lack of regular maintenance, and the proliferation of gated neighbourhoods with private control on who can access and use public spaces in semi-public neighbourhoods (Carmona et al., 2008; Chitrakar et al., 2022). Involving different stakeholders in PSM seeks to change how public policies are developed.

Values such as equity, environmental improvement, social participation, and innovation are encouraging city planners and urban designers to work on new paradigms to design or re-design public spaces (Carmona et al., 2019; Hernández Bonilla, 2012; Zamanifard et al., 2018). However, PSM challenges show that society and its aspirations are not yet fully included in the ambition to improve public space quality, and that there is scope for raising awareness of the importance thereof (Carmona et al., 2008; Zamanifard et al., 2018).

Studies on PSM (Carmona & De Magalhaes, 2006; Duivenvoorden et al., 2021) have shown how the planning, design, and maintenance phases overlap under management services, and a more holistic and integrated approach is needed in collaboration with social actors. As mentioned previously, the importance of PSM lies in the interconnection of the four dimensions of the PSM framework and the need for the involvement of different governance actors. We argue that the five identified actor groups can (and do) contribute to the (re)design, planning and maintenance of new and existing public spaces.

Applying the PSM framework to the Mexican context allows us to explore how different governance actors perceive public spaces. Additionally, public spaces in Mexico face a growing presence of the informal sector in the public space, regulatory gaps, and conflicts of interest in their management. The PSM framework helps us to systematically analyse how public spaces are managed through the different dimensions of the framework in our case studies. Finally, the Mexican context contributes to PSM literature by exploring how this approach can help make sense of a context marked by informality, ambiguities in regulatory frameworks and limited opportunities for residents to participate in PSM processes.

3. Research methods

3.1. Case study approach

To address the main research question, the case study approach was selected to explore the complex issue of the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces in Mexico. We chose to look at this real-life context due to four main aspects. First, public spaces are perceived as an essential asset for public life in the Mexican society and form an important element of a city's identity.

Second, the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces in Mexico are currently promoted by government institutions at the federal, state, and municipal levels. However, programs and projects promoted by former administrations have created policy issues such as discontinuity (projects that were initiated but never concluded) and lack of management of public spaces in marginal areas (Ribeiro-Palacios et al., 2021; Ziccardi, 2012).

Third, public spaces in Mexico are largely perceived as insecure and unequal. A recent public security study of the National Institute of Statistics and Geography found that more than 70 % of Mexicans feel unsafe in streets and open spaces, and 56 % feel insecure in public parks or recreational areas (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía, 2018). Groups or individuals engaged in criminal or antisocial activities appropriate public spaces, turning them into stigmatised or restricted places and contributing to the perception of insecurity or neglect. The general lack of attention and dedicated resources by local administrations further exasperates this impression (Kuri, 2015; Vargas et al., 2010). Particularly, public spaces need attention in marginalized

neighbourhoods, as unregulated urban growth often threatens their existence, leading to urban open voids or abandoned spaces; and where local governments are more reluctant to spend resources for their maintenance (Jasso, 2018; Portal, 2016).

Fourth, research in Mexico discusses how top-down decision-making processes affect the appropriation of public spaces and meet the needs of local residents (Fernández-Álvarez, 2017). Despite the efforts made by different levels of government in Mexico to enhance participatory processes through laws and programs (Congress of Mexico City, 2019; Instituto Municipal de Planeación, 2021), in practice, local residents are still left behind, or their voice does not have a meaningful impact on how public spaces are managed (Hernández Bonilla, 2012; Narciso, 2018).

We chose two case study cities in close geographic proximity and historical relation to analyse PSM. Mexico City and Puebla share borders at the state level and have been growing in unison. Puebla has been one of the gateways for goods and services for Mexico City since pre-Hispanic times (Garza, 2002). Since the early 1980s, both cities have belonged to the megalopolis of Central Mexico, an urban conglomerate formed by seven states in central Mexico (see Fig. 1).

The GDP per capita of Mexico City contributes 15.8 % of the national GDP with 9.2 million of inhabitants and Puebla contributes 3.2 %, with 1.5 million inhabitants (Instituto Mexicano para la Competitividad, 2021; Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía, 2021). The GDP contribution affects the budget allocated for each city. Mexico City has a considerably higher budget than Puebla since the allocation of resources is based on the amount of population to which it must provide infrastructure services for (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía, 2021; Rozas & Sánchez, 2004). Official government information

Fig. 1. Location of case study areas inside the Megalopolis of Mexico (Puebla and Mexico City).

Source: Own design with official data of the National Institute of Geography and Statistics of Mexico, 2018, and ESRI web service for orientation.

highlights differences in the public space surface per inhabitant. Mexico City has 7.5 m² of public space per inhabitant and Puebla has 2.8m², in both cases insufficient when considering the minimum surface recommended by the world health organisation of 9m² per inhabitant (Instituto Municipal de Planeacion, 2021; Secretaria de Medio Ambiente de la Ciudad de Mexico, 2017). Political differences are also seen in both cities. With a consolidated left government party for more than twenty years, Mexico City has promoted more social and urban programs, including the development of better urban infrastructure. In contrast, Puebla has a history of being more right-leaning (Llerenas, 2021), and is a city where historically urban plans and programs initiated by one government are not carried on when a different government takes charge. The inexperience and lack of human and financial resources added to each change of administration has affected PSM in Puebla (Ramírez Rosete et al., 2019; Salgado Montes, 2017).

3.2. Analytical framework

The analytical framework is based on the PSM dimensions proposed by Carmona et al. (2008): regulations in public space policies; the limited opportunities for local residents to participate in processes involving coordination of interventions; the investment in public spaces and their services; and the definition and deployment of maintenance routines. After collecting and analysing our data, we developed an analytical framework based on Carmona et al.'s (2008) PSM framework to organise, present and interpret our results. We adjusted the PSM

Framework to make it fit our study's main aims, and the adjusted framework was used to guide our analysis.

We expanded Carmona's framework by adding and operationalising 'context' and making 'social participation' an explicit dimension of the framework (see Fig. 2) to adapt the model to our specific case study. The context can significantly impact the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces. The original framework by Carmona et al. (2008) has no clear definition of the first step, "Public space policies and aspirations". It just mentions, "Public space management is anyway the governance sphere where stakeholders demands on, and aspirations for public space are articulated" (Carmona et al., 2008, p. 67). There is also a variation of the PSM model called the open space management analytical framework, on which eleven countries were analysed to identify good management practices, and where the geographical context takes relevance to understand the concerns about existing public spaces, how they look, and how they are being used (Carmona et al., 2008, p. 121).

Drawing on the subsection "Importance of public space management" (Hernández Bonilla, 2013; Li et al., 2022; Mehta, 2014; Zamanifard et al., 2018), we operationalise "Context" into three aspects: 1) the definition of what is a public space for our actors; 2) what are their aspirations, demands or actions perceived to improve public spaces; and 3) how do they perceive the conditions and functions of public spaces, related to the physical characteristics of public spaces. We consider these three aspects as important elements that need to be understood before analysing the main dimensions of the framework (Social

Fig. 2. PSM dimensions for the Mexican context. Source: own design, based on Carmona et al. (2008) & De Magalhães and Carmona (2009).

participation, Regulation, Coordination, Investment, and Maintenance).

For our case study, we consider the functions of green, open, publicly accessible spaces at a residential scale, which can be multipurpose and adopted by local residents for social, cultural or recreational activities (Stanley et al., 2012). These functions can include residents' ability to assign new purposes according to their social reality, i.e. temporary food markets, community gardens, or improvised sports facilities (De Magalhães & Carmona, 2009; Madanipour, 1999).

We added the dimension of social participation, understood as a democratic channel of consultation to collect the aspirations and actions that users require on planned and existing public spaces, with feedback to users and linkages to government institutions, because several studies (De Magalhães & Carmona, 2009; Gutiérrez Juárez et al., 2022; Mandeli, 2010, 2019; Páramo et al., 2018; Paukaeva et al., 2021; Ramírez Rosete et al., 2019) highlighted the need for enhanced involvement of residents in PSM. The original PSM model did not explicitly include social participation as a dimension on its own. This was implicitly embedded in the coordination dimension (Carmona et al., 2008). However, adding social participation as a dimension on its own helps to explore to what extent local residents are included in the process of planning, design and maintenance of public spaces and how they influence decision-making processes.

We understand the regulation dimension as the relationships between public space service providers (public and private) following urban public space policies (e.g., laws, norms, urban codes, guidelines), compliant with legislation at different government levels for the planning, design or maintenance of public spaces. These policies aim to keep public spaces in the best possible conditions through the regulation of use and conflicts between the different uses (Carmona et al., 2008; De Magalhães & Carmona, 2009).

The dimension of coordination of interventions is defined by Carmona et al. (2008), p.78 as “coordinated actions of agents whose actions impact on public space implying the coordination of public-sector services, either horizontally within and among local authority departments, or vertically among agencies at different levels of government, from the neighbourhood scale upwards”. In the original model, this dimension spans across the dimensions of regulation, investment, and maintenance with a focus on interinstitutional organisations. For our case study in Mexico, we wish to understand how the coordination is perceived by our governance actors individually and see if there are differences or similarities between the perspectives of these different actors. Making coordination to be positioned at the same level as the rest of the dimensions allows a more specific understanding of how our governance actors perceive the interventions being developed and to identify interconnections with the other dimensions.

The investment dimension is understood as the availability of public or private sector budget for public spaces services and to obtain the necessary equipment to develop quality in public spaces. The investment can also be used for different types of uses, such as introducing new technologies in public space design or maintenance routines or increasing better human and technical resources on PSM (Carmona et al., 2008). This dimension directly affects the other dimensions, such as the maintenance dimension, as the budget is required to fulfil all the required routine actions to achieve public space quality.

Following De Magalhães' and Carmona's definitions of maintenance, we define it as the routines and budget needed to maintain public spaces (Carmona et al., 2008; De Magalhães & Carmona, 2009). The maintenance dimension also refers to the management mechanism that secures the involvement of governance actors and users in designing maintenance routines, while maintaining the separation between service delivery and use (De Magalhães & Carmona, 2009).

In this study, an existing PSM framework, originally developed in a European context, was adapted and applied to the Mexican context (see Fig. 2) based on four considerations: (1) Findings from our literature review on the management of public spaces, including the work of local researchers in Mexico, point to the need to explicitly consider the

context of individual studied cities and social participation as leading dimensions in the management of public spaces (Gutiérrez Juárez et al., 2022; Páramo et al., 2018; Ramírez Rosete et al., 2019) (2) Local policies in Mexico aim to develop participatory methods to include society in the planning process, including the management and development of public spaces (Congress of Mexico City, 2019; Instituto Municipal de Planeación, 2021) (3) Our empirical data suggest that in the Mexican context, there is no framework that can be followed to understand how public spaces are being developed; (4) The original model by Carmona et al. (2008) is founded on the coordination dimension, to which the rest of dimensions are linked at the same level; in our proposed model, all dimensions are linked to understand how they mutually influence each other. Our proposed model aims to be an integrated model that gives the same level of importance to all its dimensions and considers the need to include social participation and context, as motivated by our literature review (Duijvenvoorden et al., 2021; Páramo et al., 2018; Ramírez Rosete et al., 2019) as well as analysis of the Mexican regulatory frameworks that aim for an integrated vision to carry out the required actions and ensure public spaces are managed in an integral manner (Congress of Mexico City, 2019; Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2022; Instituto Municipal de Planeación, 2021).

3.3. Data collection and analysis

We reviewed regulatory documents (see Appendix Table 3) to understand Mexico's regulatory framework on public spaces, including federal and local legislation, laws, regulations, or manuals. All regulatory documents were analysed using ATLAS.ti software, by assigning one of the 17 codes from a first reading of the latest Mexican Federal Law of Human Settlements, Territorial Order, and Urban Development (FLHSTOUD), aggregated into three themes: public space, participation, and innovation (see Fig. 11 in Appendix). The document analysis' results are incorporated into Section 4 in the regulation subsection.

The codes and the distilled themes guided the design of the interviews. The objective of the interviews was to acquire insights about the governance actors' perspectives on what constitutes a public space, the aspirations for new and redesigned public spaces, and the conditions and functions of public spaces. The data collected was also used to understand how PSM works in urban Mexico, following the proposed analytical framework for the Latin-American context in the two case studies selected (see Fig. 1).

We did not explicitly include local residents in our interviews; we considered NGOs as representing the views and interests of local residents, and directly engaging and soliciting residents' input in different projects related to the Planning, Design and Maintenance of Public Spaces (PDMPS). While it is essential to consider local residents in governance processes, we made a deliberate decision not to interview them in this stage of our research, in line with the main aim of the paper, to discuss current challenges and opportunities for public space management in Mexico. We decided to focus on the perspectives of formal governance actors currently involved in PSM. Three main aspects informed our decision: (1) Our literature review at the local level mentions that in Mexico, the opinions and perspectives of local residents are commonly ignored or deemed unimportant unless they are accompanied by legal representation, typically in the form of formal registration as a civil organisation (Casas Cárdenas, 2010; Filipe & Ramírez, 2016; Gómez Carmona, 2018); (2) Current policy guidelines suggest the improvement of participatory processes. However, currently, there are no proper conditions for residents engagement so that residents can contribute to decision-making processes in PDMPS (Congress of Mexico City, 2019; Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2022); (3) The professional experiences in Mexico of one of the authors and informal pre-fieldwork discussions with potential interviewees, including local government officials and academics from local universities, taught us that despite the recognized importance of involving local residents in decision-making processes, they are not involved in practice in the PDMPS. We argue

that this raises questions about the participatory model that exists in the country. Nevertheless, although we consider NGOs to represent the voice of local residents, we remain critical of the extent to which they indeed act according to residents wishes and interests. This is due to recent cases of corruption involving NGOs and government institutions in charge of the improvement of the urban conditions in Mexico (Nájar, 2019; Terrazas, 2009).

For the selection of interviewees, we apply a non-probability sampling technique. Our sampling methods incorporated both judgment and snowball techniques. Judgment sampling was used to identify individuals with specific expertise or attributes of interest, while snowball sampling was utilised to locate subjects through referrals from experts who possessed relevant attributes for the study (Kumar, 2011). Following Kumar's (2011) sampling techniques, we looked for actors who participate in the planning, design or maintenance of public spaces. The recruitment process began before the fieldwork investigation between June and October 2019. We reviewed official websites for contacts of local government practitioners and academics related to the PSM process. We made the initial contact by email and phone, followed by the interviews in Mexico. These interviewees referred us to other experts working on public space issues in each city. Our goal was to interview at least one actor from each group in both cities to obtain their perspectives on PSM and to identify any similarities or differences in our interviews.

Potential biases can arise in our chosen methods. For instance, the snowballing technique may result in identifying actors who share similar values regarding PSM and the judgmental technique can lead to non-reliable information from the expert or authority interviewed on PSM issues (Kumar, 2011). Another sampling bias may arise if some individuals are unable to participate due to their unavailability to be interviewed (Lune & Berg, 2017). We, therefore, considered the availability of time for our interviewees, making appointments in a convenient place and time for them. Another possible drawback is the inability to speak with high-level directors from government institutions with direct decision-making power and politicians involved in urban policy issues. We also acknowledge that potential biases and conflicts of interest may arise during the interviews. These include personal or political preferences, research interests and agenda-driven preferences.

We developed a storyboard for the semi-structured interview guide based on the document analysis (see Fig. 14). As this research involves interviews with human participants, the interview protocol was approved by the ethics committee of the university. Informed consent letters were given to our interviewees, explaining the study content and informing them about our research and data management. The interviewees were informed well in advance and in detail about this study's objectives and the use of the obtained data, and participants had to provide their written consent.

The entire fieldwork was conducted between November 2019 and January 2020 in Mexico by one of the co-authors of the study due to his previous knowledge of the country and his ability to communicate in the local language (Spanish). We scheduled about one hour per interview. Several interviewees shared with us or pointed us towards additional (mostly digital) documents related to legislation and programs (see Appendix Table 3). The interviewer recorded eighteen interviews (22 h of audio recordings) and took extensive notes during one interview where the interviewee did not wish to be recorded (see Table 4 in Appendix). Drawing on methodological guidance for conducting interviews provided by Bryman (2012), we reached our saturation point when we noticed that no new themes for discussion arose during our semi-structured interviews, when some comments and patterns began to repeat and when we had completed our interviews with at least one actor from each group in both cities (Bryman, 2012). This allowed us to have a sample – though small – with representation from each of our interviewed groups and have a diversity of perspectives based on their expertise and knowledge base related to the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces. Having one representative of each group provided the context of the field of urban planning and public spaces in

the Mexican context. Interviewing at least one actor from each group may not fully capture the diversity of all viewpoints within a group of actors. Nevertheless, the recurrent identified and persistent problems mentioned during the interviews such as the lack of maintenance, lack of economic resources, limited political will, lack of clear planning instruments and limited participatory processes were confirmed in the more open part of the interviews. This is further discussed in our findings and discussion sections.

All the documents and interviews collected are in Spanish. We developed a matrix based on the responses to the questions during the semi-structured interviews. Interview data were triangulated with other data sources, such as regulatory documents previously mentioned (see Appendix Table 3). With the raw data, we built a spreadsheet divided by the questions asked during our semi-structured interviews by each one of the groups of actors. An example of the first three questions can be seen in Appendix Table 6. With the interviews systematically organised and digitally transcribed, we subsequently elaborated a table of actors' points of view (Appendix Table 5) to locate similar or different topics, framings, and perspectives, and organise the findings for our further discussion. Parts of the interviews were translated into English to provide illustrative quotes. We took notes during the interviews and when visiting specific public space locations. We focused on the visible conditions of public spaces, maintenance, and social participation challenges (see Appendix Fig. 14). The field notes were used to annotate key ideas and topics discussed during our semi-structured interviews and how we observed the conditions of the public spaces we visited, how they were used, and to comprehensively understand the context of the public spaces we visited in Mexico (see Appendix Fig. 14). The field note observations were followed by photographic records, which provided deeper insights about the visible characteristics of the different public spaces we visited.

We took photographs during the fieldwork in November 2019. Written and photographic records are valuable sources of evidence for observing public space dynamics (Flowerdew, 2008; Gehl & Svarre, 2013; Mandeli, 2019). The main objective of PSM is to achieve quality in public spaces. Hence, the purpose of the photographs is to observe whether this objective is realised regarding the appearance of public spaces in our two case study cities. We use this method to visually document the current situation of public spaces for illustration and gather a nuanced understanding of the physical context (Lune & Berg, 2017). Understanding the physical context of public spaces is relevant to comprehend their use and how they function in daily life. The research ethics committee granted a positive advice for the procedure of taking photographs in this study. When taking photographs, we were mindful of respecting people's privacy and were cautious when taking pictures in areas where photos might be frowned upon (Flowerdew, 2008; Gehl & Svarre, 2013; Lune & Berg, 2017; Mandeli, 2019). The photographs were taken using a smartphone, and contextual information such as the location and date were recorded for each photograph. Visual examples of the photographs can be seen in Chapter 4 of this study and the locations in Fig. 3. The photographs, fieldwork notes and interviews were integrated and triangulated for our data analysis.

The selection of the specific locations to visit was based firstly on the definition used for this study (see subsection 'Public spaces and their importance for cities'), particularly focusing on public spaces located at the neighbourhood scale. Secondly, we also intentionally visited public spaces with contrasting levels of maintenance, based on suggestions made by the actors we interviewed and using the local knowledge and prior experience of one of the co-authors. In Mexico City, we visited two locations in the Historical Centre and the Tepito Neighbourhood with the guidance of one of the NGOs we interviewed. We visited three neighbourhoods in Puebla, two low-income and one high-income locations. Thirdly, we visited locations inside each city's municipal administrative boundary, based on advice given by local experts (See Fig. 3). When taking the photographs, we were mindful respecting people's privacy and were cautious when taking pictures in areas where taking

Fig. 3. Site visit locations in Mexico City and Puebla. Source: own design.

photos might be frowned upon (Flowerdew, 2008; Gehl & Svarre, 2013; Lune & Berg, 2017; Mandeli, 2019). We undertook efforts to produce reliable findings by meticulously designing and documenting every aspect of data collection and analysis in a systematic manner, complemented by the tailored and rigorously applied PSM framework, ensuring the utmost accuracy and credibility of our study's findings.

The image below (Fig. 4) illustrates the data collection and analysis process conducted for this study.

4. Actors' perspectives on PSM in Mexico

4.1. Context: public space definition

In the case study areas, all the interviewed actors consider public spaces as very important areas for residents, which should be multi-functional, freely accessible, focused on social interactions and collective use, but also allowing activities such as street vending. The NGOs interpret public spaces as places for protest and social action, sometimes used as a channel for accessing decision-making processes. Interviewed academics and government actors added that the quality of life in open spaces could be assessed by measuring the number of people who use them, and the planting of endemic vegetation could help to regulate the urban environment in big cities.

4.2. Context: aspirations of public spaces

All interviewed actors aspire for public spaces that are green, properly designed, and able to accommodate social interaction: “they must

be comfortable to the eye, with green areas and resting spots, pleasant for pedestrians and cyclists and need to promote social interactions between other residents” (College of Urban planners and designers of the state of Puebla, translation).²

However, NGOs and academics expressed concerns that criminal activities and insecurity impeded social functions. The perception of insecurity has led society to focus on the aspiration to get safe, secure, and illuminated public spaces, with day and night activities. Mexico City's Tepito neighbourhood is such as case and points to how far the vision of the green and inclusive public space is removed from reality (see Fig. 5). Only government institutions at the federal and local levels mentioned the importance of the management of public spaces and considered their fair distribution within cities as an essential element to achieve public space quality.

4.3. Context: conditions and functions of public space

We can summarise the interviewees' perception of the current conditions of public spaces in four specific adjectives: neglected, forgotten, insecure, and dilapidated. This very negative perception is especially evident in marginal, rural, or peripheral areas of the Mexican cities, where there is a general feeling of being left behind, with a lack of cultural, recreational, or social activities, and a severe lack of

² Original quote in Spanish: “debes ser agradables a la vista del usuario, con áreas verdes y espacios de descanso, cómodos para el ciclista y el peatón. Necesitan promover la interacción social entre sus residentes.”

Fig. 4. Process for data collection and analysis.

Source: own design.

Fig. 5. Public spaces surrounded by informal commerce in Tepito Neighbourhood in Mexico City.

Source: Author, photograph taken in January 2020.

management and maintenance. In contrast, high-income neighbourhoods (often gated communities) have better maintenance due to internal investments of the residents living inside these gated communities (See Fig. 6) (interviews with Federal and Local Government).

These inequalities are aggravated by the Federal Government due to its focus on preserving and maintaining touristic, historical, and central public spaces (interviews with NGOs and government actors). Most interviewed architecture/urban planning firms actors point to an unfair distribution of public spaces across the city and weaker investment in less touristic areas. Based on our interviews with all governance actors, the most common explanations for the poor conditions in public spaces can be summarised as follows (See Table 1):

Public space functions are related to informal commercial, recreational, cultural, social, or religious uses. Their democratic and political functions are also part of the Mexican culture (interviews with local government, architecture/urban planning firms and academics). The four groups of governance actors mentioned the strong economic value of public spaces through the informal sector in Mexico. This comes from the pre-colonial tradition of street markets, as local residents appropriate public spaces for informal commercial activities, such as flea markets. However, today's public spaces are not designed for this purpose: "Mexico has a tradition of over 500 years of using public spaces for

commercial purposes (See Fig. 7), but these traditional aspects were ignored by decision-makers of the city"³ (interview with the NGO Barriopolis). This insight is supported by statistical data showing that 72 % of the population works in the informal sector in Puebla versus 47 % in Mexico City, creating difficulties in managing informality on public spaces in the city of Puebla (Camberos Castro & Bracamontes Nevarez, 2021).

Officially, such economic functions are not foreseen, and public spaces are intended to be used for recreational purposes, to increase the green areas, to integrate communities, and preserve the ecological equilibriums. The Federal Law of Human Settlements, Territorial Order, and Urban Development (LHSTOUDL) suggests that public spaces may not be used for other purposes that can create social discomfort (Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2016). Such regulation stifles other uses and functions that emerge as per the needs of public space users and limits the possibilities of spaces to be adapted and accommodated accordingly. However, NGOs and academics mentioned that there are more criminal

³ Original quote in Spanish: "México tiene una tradición de mas de 500 años de utilizar los espacios públicos para fines comerciales, pero los tomadores de decisiones han ignorado los aspectos básicos de esta tradición en la ciudad."

Fig. 6. Outside view from the new gated communities in the Angelopolis neighbourhood in Puebla.
Source: Author, photograph taken in January 2020.

Table 1
Main explanations of the poor conditions of public space in Mexico.

Explanation of poor conditions of public spaces	Actors mentioning them
There is a lack of general technical and operative tools for the planning, management, and maintenance of public spaces at the public sector level.	Federal and local government, NGOs.
Real estate developers are converting public space into private development conforming to the lobbied Mexican legislation, which is unclear and presents gaps at local levels.	Local Government, Academics, NGOs.
Public-private partnerships design spaces with a consumer focus instead of seeking to generate a social or environmental impact.	Architecture/urban planning firms, Academics and NGOs.
There is a lack of promotion and awareness of the importance of public spaces for the city.	NGOs, Academics, Local Government.
There is a lack of budget assigned by public institutions for the development and management of public spaces.	Local Government, NGOs, Academics.
Visions of how to plan and manage public spaces diverge.	All the actors
Public spaces are perceived as a luxury rather than a social need by investors and some decision-makers.	Architecture/urban planning firms, NGOs, Academics.
Coordination between the different government levels is inefficient.	Local Government, Academics, NGOs.
Social actors are not adequately involved in the development and management of public spaces.	All the actors
People feel insecure and organised crime is prevalent.	NGOs and Academics
People feel safer and are attracted to commercial areas such as shopping centres rather than open areas.	Federal and Local Government, Academics and NGOs.
New gated communities with private open spaces are appearing	Academics, NGOs.

Source: Based on conducted interviews made on fieldwork in Mexico.

or illegal activities in neglected public spaces due to the abandonment of government institutions to attend issues related to drugs, prostitution, or thievery (See Fig. 8).

4.4. Social participation

All groups of actors mentioned in their interviews that efforts are being made to involve residents in the processes of planning. However, it is not yet a common practice, and there is still a lack of involvement on topics related to public spaces or in the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces. Government practitioners at the federal and local

levels mentioned superficial social participation and are aware of the problem. Even the architecture/urban planning firms, academics, and NGOs felt that creating collaborative solutions between government and other governance actors can develop better, more inclusive solutions for public spaces.

The first contact of residents on issues related to the development and management of public spaces is with government institutions, which usually do not involve other actors in the process. Local government interviewees shared that residents usually petition government institutions to solve issues related to maintaining or renovating a specific public space. However, there are no proper channels of communication to solve deeper issues due to poor institutional coordination. The opposite is the case with academics and NGOs; their first contact on public space issues is with residents, and they sometimes even actively avoid government institutions. This is mostly due to a conflict of interest between government plans or public-private partnerships and the interest of local residents. For the architecture/urban planning firms, participatory processes often have low relevance and no meaningful impact, as most of the time, social requests are not considered in the final project decisions (interview with Entorno Paisaje and Thorsten Architects).

We observed that government actors in Puebla City mentioned no involvement with residents on PSM issues or other public space programs (interview with government officials in Puebla). More social involvement and direct interaction were noted in Mexico City through an institution called the Authority of Public Space; however, this body was abolished in 2019, and the tasks and responsibilities were assigned to two other entities, the ministry of mobility and the ministry of public works in Mexico City (interview with a local government official from Mexico City).

The federal government usually works in coordination with the state and municipal levels and superficially interacts with other actors or delegating actions to local institutions as the scale of action is at the national level. Government officials often inform residents about the projects being developed. During interviews with government officials at the local and federal levels, three common levels of social participation were mentioned: consultation, involvement, and collaboration or co-production. Nevertheless, there is no evidence of direct involvement of residents in larger projects. Efforts are limited to consulting public opinion on a project already prepared. As NGOs, academics, and local government highlighted, residents still do not have decision-making power and influence over most public space projects.

Fig. 7. Flea market over streets in the city centre of Mexico City.
Source: Author, photograph taken in December 2019.

Fig. 8. Neglected public space in the Villa Verde Neighbourhood, Puebla.
Source: Author, photograph taken in January 2020.

4.5. Regulation

The document review reveals that the Mexican regulatory framework follows a hierarchical setup, where every decision related to the urban space is based on the Political Constitution of the United States of Mexico of 1917 (*Cámara de Diputados del H. Congreso de la Unión, 2018*).

Programs, norms, planning policies and regulations at different government levels are also based on the Constitution.⁴ At the top of the hierarchy of these plans, norms and regulations is the national plan formulated by the president, who is the head of the state and the government (Fig. 9). This national plan includes the proposed programs to be carried out during the presidential period. The current plan (2021–2024) focuses on social policies, including the sustainable development of cities, and the development of an urban and housing program, which includes rehabilitation and improvement of public spaces (*Gobierno de México, 2019*).

At the state and municipal level, each governor and the mayor have

to present their development plans as well, which formulate their regulatory frameworks and strategic targets in accordance with the national plan (see Table 2). The development plans of our two case study cities aim to improve the conditions of public spaces, and this goal is reflected in regulatory instruments such as the Law of Urban Development of Mexico City, the initiative of Law of public space for Mexico City or the Municipal plan of development of Puebla 2018–2021 (*Cámara de Diputados del H. Congreso de la Unión, 2018; Congress of Mexico City, 2019; Instituto Nacional para el Federalismo y el Desarrollo Municipal, 2019*). The international policies adopted in the regulatory planning framework are commonly mentioned at the federal level, in regulations and official government press-releases (*Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2016; Secretaría de Desarrollo Agrario Territorial y Urbano, 2019*). The country's participation in the international efforts to achieve the SDGs and the adoption of the New Urban Agenda, as a roadmap to promote sustainable cities in Mexico are explicitly highlighted.

During the former president's term of office (Enrique Peña Nieto, 2012–2018), a federal ministry called “The Ministry of Agrarian, Territorial and Urban Development” (SEDATU) was created in 2013 (*Subsecretaría de Desarrollo Urbano y Vivienda, 2014*). In 2016, the SEDATU presented the Federal Law LHSTOUDL (*Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2016*). This was the first federal legislation that operationalised and

⁴ The translation of official names and information of regulatory and legal documents was made by the first author.

Regulatory planning framework of Mexico

Fig. 9. The regulatory planning framework in Mexico. Source: own design, based on reviewed regulatory documents.

Table 2
General national urban planning system in Mexico.

Government levels	Laws	Regulatory framework: plans and programs	Executor	Government levels of coordination	Actions	Actors involved
Federal	General Law of Human Settlements, Land Management	National Urban Development Program	Secretariat of Agrarian, Land, and Urban Development	National State Municipal Neighbourhood	- Develop laws - Assign budget - Execute large scale projects	Residents Private sector Academics NGOs
	Urban Development program in Mexico	Program for Urban Improvement.				
State	State laws on human settlements	State Urban Development Plans and Programs	(Ministry of mobility, Urban development or public works)	State Metropolitan Municipal Regional	- Develop Plans - Approve Plans - Execute	
Municipal/ Local		Municipal urban development plans	Departments of Urban Planning Mobility, Infrastructure or Public Works	Federal State Municipal	- Approve local level plans - Execute at a neighbourhood scale	

Source: own design, based on Rivera Borrayo and Orozco Alvarado (2009).

connected the terms of urban development, public space, management, and social participation. Specifically, it defines public spaces as: “open spaces or land that belong to human settlements intended for use, enjoyment or collective use, with generalised access and free transit”⁵ (Diario Oficial de la Federacion, 2016).

While regulation did accentuate the importance of public spaces and

⁵ Original quote in Spanish: “áreas, espacios abiertos o predios de los asentamientos humanos destinados al uso, disfrute o aprovechamiento colectivo, de acceso generalizado y libre tránsito.”

social participation in the current national plan for the period 2018–2024 (Diario Oficial de la Federacion, 2016; Gobierno de México, 2019), our interviews also revealed that not every governance actor is aware of how the Mexican legislation works in relation to the management of public spaces, including the LHSTOUDL which also promotes the importance of social participation in the development of public spaces. Interviews with academics and NGOs in both cities foreground the lack of instruments or indices to evaluate the current conditions of public spaces. According to them, sometimes legislations are used to justify projects without previous studies, ignoring the local planning policies and urban development plans. Social actors are often left out in

Table 5
Example of the table of actors' points of view; the data collected was organised on topics, and from there, the findings were obtained according to the responses of each government actor.

How different governance actors understand the role and meaning of public space.																			
General Perception of Public Space					Importance for the city					Characteristics of an attractive PS					Common functions of PS				
Essential element					Highly important					Colourful and comfortable					Multifunctional				
NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed
Social interaction					Absorb Urban expansion					Green spaces					Informal commerce				
NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed
Open to everyone					Combat insecurity					promote social interactions					Recreational functions				
NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed
Regulated by the government					Improve cities					Offers environmental services					Political				
NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed
Space that is not private					Creates social coexistence					Quality in their design (All actors)					Cultural				
NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed
Accessible					Influence quality of life					Good management					Externalities promote Economic (All actors)				
NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed
Democratic space					Promote human interaction					Safe and secure					Illegal or criminal functions				
NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed
Surrounded by a built environment					Creates quality of life					Accessible and inclusive					Cosmological or Religious				
NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed
Multifunctional					Opposite of the private space					Prioritized in marginal areas					Mobility or transit				
NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed	NGO	Aca	Prv	Loc	Fed

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation.
 Aca: Academics.
 Prv: Private actors (Urban/Architecture consultancy companies).
 Loc: Local government.
 Fed: Federal government.

co-creative or participatory design processes and are only consulted about their opinion when projects have already started to be developed.

Existing public spaces do not have a clear definition of regulatory frameworks about their maintenance and which actors are responsible for them. According to the interviews with government institutions in Mexico City and Puebla, several factors determine who will be responsible for the repair or maintenance in the event of damage to a public space. This varies depending on the government institution responsible for public spaces, the level of damage applied, and which institutions are required to repair the damage. All this leads us to the first challenge of inter-institutional coordination (Delgadillo, 2018). No one wants to take responsibility due to factors such as institutional rivalries or lack of investment, hence promoting institutional disinterest and administrative mismanagement and giving priority to other projects.

4.6. Coordination

The interviews revealed the involvement of diverse government institutions such as ministries of mobility, planning institutes, ministries of tourism or infrastructure work and ministries of parks and recreation. Policies and legislation obligate institutions to coordinate their actions with social agents (Diario Oficial de la Federacion, 2016; Gobierno Constitucional del Estado de Puebla, 2017); however, academics and government officials mentioned that social involvement is fragmented, and when residents are involved, the decisions made have no relevance on topics related to public spaces.

Between external institutions such as NGOs, universities, or the private sector, coordination happens through public-private agreements or partnerships to participate in the development of specific projects, usually through consultancy or project development contracts. Social mobilisation is becoming more active to counter prevalent decision-making processes. NGOs, for example, obtain funding from government institutions to develop social interventions in public spaces and coordinate actions with residents to promote and invite other social actors to participate in decision-making processes: “New partnerships with the private sector can cause that public spaces disappear through public-private investments, which usually come along with real state depredation. This is caused by failed public policies, the extinction of green areas and land speculation”⁶ (interview with academic from the Autonomous University of Puebla, faculty of architecture).

The private sector can be divided into two different groups. The first is comprised of architecture or urbanism firms hired to develop proposals for projects related to public spaces. Government tender contracts usually request a participatory element, but the final result does not consider the feedback obtained in participatory processes. The second

⁶ Original quote in Spanish: “Es posible que desaparezcan los espacios públicos debido a las asociaciones publico privadas debido y a la inversión con el sector privado, parte de la depredación de las inmobiliarias. Esto es a causa de los resultados de políticas públicas fallidas, la extinción de áreas verdes y la especulación del suelo.”

group are private investors, most of the time real estate developers who want to invest in urban projects, or consultancy companies that developed a proposal and seek to create public-private partnerships or to manage some public spaces, and who have to comply to the project's request on social participation without any social impact on the final project (interviews with Entorno Paisaje and Thorsten Architects):

There are no state or municipal laws that promote the development of public spaces; the Authority of Public Space was the only institution linked with developing public spaces, that I am aware of, but it disappeared overnight.⁷ (interview with academic from the Autonomous Metropolitan University).

The federal level has more resources and is, therefore, less reliant on private investors. There is some collaboration with state and municipal institutions; for example, the 2019-initiated federal "Program for Urban Improvement" aims to involve society in issues related to the renovation and improvement of public spaces (see Fig. 9) (Avalos, 2020). Nevertheless, the efforts made at the federal level to promote the development of public spaces are scarce and at odds with independent actions taken by local government; the lack of inter-institutional coordination, the lack of knowledge of federal legislation and political differences affect the decision-making and the production of public spaces. For example, the Authority of Public Space of Mexico City – the only local institution in the country focused on the planning, design, and management of public spaces – was abolished due to the poor administration of the agency; the Metropolitan Institute of Planning of the state of Puebla was also abolished with some projects related to the development and management of public spaces.

4.7. Investment

According to the federal government, a big problem is the lack of coordination between the different government levels and other external actors. Resulting adverse effects include inefficient or misallocated budgetary means, no political will to focus on public spaces or corruption, and others:

We had a neoliberal model in the cities. Also, there are a lot of administrative issues in the municipalities that prevent the improvement of the conditions of public spaces, like lack of budgetary resources, poor allocation of the budget or corruption are the main issues.⁸ (interview with Academic from the Institute of Social Sciences and Humanities).

NGOs and local governments mentioned that working as a social initiative is too costly; the lack of financial means prevents them from acquiring proper equipment or covering the high upfront costs for new innovative technologies or tools to improve public spaces. Lack of funding is, thus, an important barrier to implementing innovative solutions in the development and management of public spaces (interview with Barriopolis).

4.8. Maintenance

According to academics and government practitioners, maintaining public spaces in Mexico City faces different challenges. First, there is a need for management plans for public spaces. Second, a lack of cultural, social, or recreational activities leads to deserted public spaces. Third, there is a lack of awareness among non-governmental actors of the

⁷ Original quote in Spanish: "No hay leyes municipales o estatales que promuevan un desarrollo real de espacios públicos, la Autoridad del Espacio Público fue la única institución más relacionada al desarrollo de espacios público que yo conozco, pero desapareció de la noche a la mañana."

⁸ Original quote in Spanish: "Teníamos un modelo neoliberal en las ciudades. También hay una gran cantidad de problemas administrativos en los municipios que no permiten mejorar las condiciones de los espacios públicos, como falta de presupuesto, la mala asignación del presupuesto o la corrupción".

important role that they can play in the maintenance of public spaces. Also, an academic from the Autonomous Metropolitan University and two government practitioners mentioned that local actors, mostly neighbourhood associations in marginal areas, do not have the resources to support the maintenance of public spaces, in the case they exist. "Mexico City has plenty of green areas but in bad shape and bad conditions.... Some public spaces have a proper urban design but are not well maintained"⁹ (interview with Thorsten Architects).

In Puebla City, the lack of maintenance is highly visible in some public spaces, creating a perception of abandonment and insecurity. For example, NGOs, academics, and the federal government respondents mentioned that maintenance efforts benefit from private investments and are prioritised in the city centre (see Fig. 10) and high-income neighbourhoods. At the same time, peripheral areas of Mexico City and Puebla remain neglected (see Fig. 8) (interviews with the Autonomous University of Puebla, the College of Urban Planners and designers of Puebla and federal government actors). Government institutions at all levels are tasked with providing maintenance to public spaces, mostly through the cleaning service agencies (H. Ayuntamiento de Puebla 2018–2021, 2020). However, coordination between institutions and other actors needs to be substantially improved: "If public spaces are well lit and maintained, the proliferation of criminal activities can be avoided; the perception of these places could change, and its users would start taking better care of them"¹⁰ (interview with a former collaborator of the abolished Authority of Public Space).

Our research identified three major differences between the case study cities. First, differences in the institutional setup supporting the PSM. Mexico City has planning institutions with more resources, clearer responsibilities, and the legacy of promoting the country's first ministry of public spaces. In contrast, the government institutions in Puebla act less coordinated, with local institutions working individually on public space projects and collaborating only when necessary. Second, regarding regulatory frameworks, Mexico City has more specific laws promoting the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces, including a new initiative of the law of public spaces that has not been clearly defined (Congress of Mexico City, 2019). Puebla's legislation instead has gaps concerning the responsibilities for the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces and lacks dedicated legal and political instruments to manage them. Third, academics and local government representatives mentioned the proliferation of informal commerce in the central areas of both cities due to a lack of job opportunities, making it more challenging to manage informal commerce in public spaces. However, Mexico City has made efforts to control and manage informality, such as the "Chambeando Ando" law initiative, which seeks to regulate informal commerce on public spaces in Mexico City (Ramirez, 2020). A summary of the findings of our extended PSM Framework can be seen in the appendix in Fig. 12.

5. Discussion

Studies have emphasised the crucial role of the urban context in the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces (De Magalhães & Freire Trigo, 2017; Zamanifard et al., 2018). From the public space management perspective, Carmona et al. (2008) proposed a PSM framework with four dimensions: regulation, investment, maintenance and coordination, previously described in this study in chapter four of research methods (Carmona et al., 2008). Our study expands the

⁹ Original quote in Spanish: "La ciudad de Mexico tiene varias áreas verdes que se ven mal y estan en malas condiciones.... Algunos espacios públicos tienen un buen diseño urbano, pero no están correctamente mantenidas".

¹⁰ Original quote in Spanish: "si los espacios públicos presentan buena iluminación y se mantienen, se puede evitar la proliferación de actividades delictivas, la percepción de los lugares podría cambiar y comenzar a ser más cuidados por sus usuarios".

Fig. 10. Mexico City street in the city centre.
Source: Own photography taken in January 2020.

analytical framework with a ‘context’ section and a ‘social participation’ dimension (see Fig. 2) to understand how public spaces are defined and perceived in Latin America, specifically in the Mexican case. Previous studies that adopted Carmona et al. (2008)¹ PSM framework in non-European contexts also implicitly highlighted the need to consider these two dimensions (Chitrakar et al., 2022; Mandeli, 2010). Our findings suggest that public space management in our case study shares some challenges with the European context related to uncoordinated efforts to maintain public spaces, lack of investment due to competing political priorities, privatisation of public spaces, and a strong focus on aesthetics rather than functionalities.

Our empirical data points to a shared understanding of definitions of public space between all four groups of governance actors, the regulatory documents and our own definition (De Magalhães & Carmona, 2009; Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2016; Madanipour, 1999). From a PSM perspective, a shared definition implies no significant gaps in interpreting fundamental aspects of public spaces. Qualities that can lead to achieving successful PSM, and can be done with a deeper focus on the spatial form of the cities and the immediate context where public spaces are located, promoting activities with interest to local residents, and improving the image and quality of a place that is perceived as neglected (Carmona, 2010b; Gehl, 2004; Portal, 2016).

Following the PSM analytical framework adapted for our case study (Fig. 2), in this section we discuss the differences across PSM studies reported in the literature and the different approaches of the PSM dimensions that we found in our case study.

Latin America imported European and American urban planning models from the 19th century until now as a symbol of modernity (Díaz-Márquez, 2019), including the management of public spaces (Páramo et al., 2018). Our literature review highlights the need for a more in-depth exploration of PSM from a Latin American and, specifically, Mexican perspective. The application of the PSM framework in non-European contexts shared differences and similarities in our case study in Latin America. It was observed that Mexico has a well-developed regulatory framework and legislations that promotes participatory processes aligned with international agendas, compared to other contexts, such as Nepal and Saudi Arabia (Chitrakar, 2015; Mandeli, 2019). Nevertheless, Mexico shares similar challenges with the two countries, such as the lack of coordination among government institutions, informality, the lack of maintenance of public spaces and the need of regulatory frameworks to be effectively translated into practice (Chitrakar, 2015; Mandeli, 2010; Ramírez Rosete et al., 2019). The studies in Nepal and Saudi Arabia highlighted the need to consider the local context and

the role of social participation in managing public spaces. By including these two dimensions in our framework proved valuable to make the framework fit for the Mexican case.

In the Mexican context, the functionalities mentioned by other scholars were also supported by the views shared during the interviews. The actors understood public spaces as places for collective use and free access, for social functions as well as for interaction, manifestation, commerce or leisure (Carmona, 2010a; Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2016; Madanipour, 1999). Other similarities relate to the perception of public spaces as a social necessity instead of a luxury. Social participation is explicitly mentioned as needed to achieve consensus for decision-making processes for PSM. Local residents want to become more active, and through their participation, it is possible to avoid conflicts of interest and give greater credibility to government actions related to public spaces.

However, for the second contextual aspect – actors’ aspirations of public spaces – we observed that the regulatory definitions and planning instruments in Mexico are not aligned with what is seen in practice and what government actors, NGOs, and academics aspire to achieve. All actors mentioned that many public spaces look neglected, forgotten, insecure, and in the process of decay. However, they aspire for safe, secure, healthy, accessible, and well-designed public spaces. Worthy to mention is that there does not seem to be an explicit need for new public spaces by the interviewees, which could be due to the inability of current government institutions to maintain existing public spaces in good condition (Delgado, 2018; Secretaría de Desarrollo Social, 2010).

The third contextual aspect – current conditions and functions of public spaces – also shows a discrepancy between what is officially on paper and what is seen in practice. Our empirical data shows that the Mexican regulatory framework aims to improve public spaces’ current functions and to foster social interactions: however, these are yet to materialise in reality (Carmona, 2015; Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2016; Kuri, 2015; Portal, 2016).

The review of the PSM dimension of regulation reveals that the country is attempting to improve public space conditions at all government levels through the current national plan (2019–2024), the first official definition of public spaces in federal law (LHSTOUDL), and various programs at state and local level (Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2016; Gobierno de México, 2019). Regulation is the foundation for the operability of the other four dimensions. In the Mexican context, the recent efforts to define the purpose and importance of public spaces still need regulatory instruments to secure the compliance of public space policies; lacking clear instruments to measure, comply and achieve the

development of public spaces, can lead to developing projects based on interpretations that do not seek to improve the quality of public spaces, nor how to manage them. The previous obstacles are not exclusive to the Mexican case, as they have similarly materialized in other contexts, as demonstrated by the scenarios observed in Saudi Arabia and Nepal (Chitrakar et al., 2022; Mandeli, 2010).

NGOs and the architecture/urban planning firms stated that some regulations are used to justify projects without following norms or manuals, leading consultancy firms to interpret in their own way how public spaces should be designed and developed. This contrasts with the regulatory dimension's purpose of compliance with public space policies. The lack of instruments to measure which public spaces need to be prioritised or how they are developed creates a gap between inter-institutional agencies in achieving objectives and services; there are no master plans or planning instruments focusing on the development of public spaces.

The PSM dimension of coordination is the main concern expressed by government levels, largely due to the fragmented coordination between government institutions and other governance actors. In the Mexican context, the main complaint is the lack of tools to develop the tasks for the planning, design and maintenance of public spaces; this includes the lack of internet, software and sometimes even a computer, which makes it difficult to develop coordinated solutions. The telephone, social media such as WhatsApp or personal visits continue to be the main way to share and coordinate efforts between government institutions.

Due to the poor coordination, resident organisations shun contact with government institutions and take actions on their own initiative, developing public space interventions without official permission from local authorities. This “do-it-yourself” activism reverberates some trends towards tactical urbanism or guerrilla urbanism, observed in Canada, Mexico, and Colombia (Lydon et al., 2012).

The only actor that seems to benefit from having direct contact with the government is the architecture/urban planning firms. Due to political decisions and institutional interest as well as successful lobbying, decision-makers and the private sector started to have a close relationship, including some cases of corruption, as it was found with the former secretary in charge of the federal agency SEDATU (Auerbach, 2012; Delgadillo, 2018; Low, 2005). The interviews with NGOs, academics and the architecture/urban planning firms revealed how private investors acquire contracts for the planning, design, or maintenance of public spaces, with corruption playing a key role. With the transfer of management responsibilities to private actors, the government is becoming even more dependent on the private sector, further increasing its influence on how the city looks and how it is managed. The result is that corporate interests are coming to dominate public spaces (Carmona, 2019; De Magalhães & Carmona, 2006).

The investment dimension is a decisive aspect related to coordination in the Mexican case. Insufficient budget and its poor allocation are a crippling problem, with peripheral or marginal areas being neglected and investment flowing into high-class residential, touristic, or central areas. This finding is in line with other studies (Carmona et al., 2008; Zamanifard et al., 2018) that observed the same concentration of inequality. Government practitioners mentioned the need to strengthen governmental working groups with technical expertise and professional backgrounds regarding public space development.

The maintenance dimension aims to apply what has been developed in the previous dimensions. However, it also gets affected by a domino effect caused by issues in the previous dimensions, such as lack of coordination or investment that affects how maintenance is given to public spaces. According to Carmona et al. (2008), this dimension should follow the available regulation and policies to improve the physical conditions of public spaces, including all technical, budgetary aspects and public consultations to support actions on how to maintain them through other actors (Carmona et al., 2008). However, we identified several challenges that impede the desired progress: the lack of operability and coordination between government institutions and other

actors on how to maintain or who will be responsible for the public spaces; the lack and frequent misallocation of resources; the constant social concern on the physical conditions of public spaces; the lack of effective social participation; and the need to create awareness among residents about the important role it needs to play. Lack of capacities and resources were also found in other domains of urban management (e.g., investment and coordination).

The additional PSM dimension proposed by this paper, social participation, stresses the need for and importance of involving residents in PSM as there are limited opportunities for participatory processes. Despite implementing new planning policies, the existing opportunities frequently lack relevance and fail to create any significant impact, thereby giving rise to long-term policy issues. The interviews confirmed the need for strong involvement of residents – exclusionary practices persist, and there is only superficial citizen participation in public space development. These findings reflect the results from other European and Non-European studies that emphasised how the social and psychological needs of inhabitants are being ignored and the functions and social relations in the city are being disrupted (Carmona et al., 2008; Chitrakar et al., 2022; Duivenvoorden et al., 2021; Mandeli, 2019).

Our research highlighted differences between our two cases. First, we learned that the size of the population and national policies affect the investment of public infrastructure received by the federal government and how it is allocated at the local level. For example, Puebla in the year 2020 allocated 72 % less budget to urban infrastructure than in 2019, and Mexico City 32 % less, directly affecting the development of public spaces (Guadarrama et al., 2021). This was confirmed by the federal and local governments interviewed, triggered by a national austerity policy that affects investment in public spaces. Secondly, we found some attempts to improve PSM in Mexico City, creating institutions such as the authority of public spaces or the laboratory for Mexico City. Puebla does not have or is developing similar institutions focused only on improving PSM. Thirdly, in both cities, the regulatory frameworks are distinct. There have been more efforts to develop regulatory frameworks and planning instruments in Mexico City, while Puebla continues to fall behind on public space legislation. Lastly, according to our government interviewees at the federal and local levels, political and ideological differences affect how public spaces are being managed in both cities. Hence, the two selected cases enable insightful comparisons of geographic scales, budget investments, and how public spaces are potentially managed (Jasso, 2018).

6. Conclusion

This paper used the PSM analytical framework to elucidate the challenges and opportunities of PSM in the Mexican context. We analysed this issue via two case studies, Mexico City and Puebla City, in order to provide a clearer understanding of current PSM conditions in Central Mexico. At the conceptual level, Carmona's PSM framework helped us to systematically analyse how public spaces are managed in the case studies. However, different interpretations of how public spaces are managed in the Mexican context – in contrast to the European – made us add a context section and make social participation explicit. This paper, therefore, demonstrates the reasons and steps we followed to make an existing PSM framework fit for our empirical context of use, a process that can potentially have applicability beyond the Mexican context. Claiming generalisability of our findings or the applicability of our framework in diverse local or international contexts would require a testing process, which later could lead to applying our approach to those contexts.

Through document review and interviews, effectively complementing each other, we confirmed that the three challenges prevalent in PSM literature hamper PSM in Mexico: At the intra-governmental level, (1) there is a lack of coordination between government institutions. Regarding interactions with other actors, the government is (2) increasingly relying on the private sector for the development and

management of public spaces, while (3) providing limited opportunities for local residents to participate in PSM processes.

It is important to mention conflicting points of view among our interviewed actors regarding the PSM. The first difference in points of view is the evident lack of trust in government institutions among the NGOs, academics and architecture/urban planning firms. Government institutions are perceived as making decisions out of personal interest due to their ongoing political agenda, conflicts of interest, corruption, or lack of will to keep on course public space projects. The second aspect is the difficulty in institutional coordination among federal and local government actors. The federal government is perceived as having a degree of institutional coordination at the federal level. However, at the local level, inconsistent or misinterpreted public policies, political or institutional differences due to personal interest, and the lack of resource allocation by the federal government result in the perception of a lack of institutional coordination. A third situation perceived is the application of regulatory frameworks for PSM. The government's position is to abide by what the regulatory framework says. However, NGOs, academics and the architecture/urban planning firms differ on what is mentioned in the current regulatory instruments, such as broad definitions of how public space should be planned, designed and maintained, allowing different interpretations of the law at personal convenience and without precise regulatory instruments for PSM, creating a conflict of understanding of what the law mentions and what has to be done in practice.

Despite some PSM successes, many vaguely shared ideas on how to improve and maintain public spaces - even among government actors - remain. Government agencies at all levels (municipal, state, and federal) tend to have more interconnected relationships and usually focus on large-scale projects; smaller projects suffer from incoordination.

For that reason, the extended framework presented enabled us to explain several issues: the meaning of public spaces and their physical perception by governance actors; the effects of coordination and transfer of PSM responsibilities on other governance actors; the level of social participation in PSM; and the effects of investment and maintenance on the physical conditions of public spaces.

Our research focused on the opportunities and challenges of PSM. Nonetheless, future research could explore the different typologies and functionalities of public spaces in more detail. Since our interviewees mixed different scales and typologies when giving their definition of public spaces, this limited the level of detail possible. Some functions might require a specific management regime according to the different scales (i.e., Metropolitan, city level, intermediate or residential level) and different types of public spaces (e.g., street, green open area, square). To enhance the generalisability and validity of our study on this aspect, further studies at different scales could bring valuable insights for the diverse management regimes.

Our results foreground that local and international government institutions should focus on three main aspects in PSM practice. First, they should explore ways to enhance their interaction and coordination with governance actors and residents in the planning, design and maintenance of public spaces. Second, they need to seek meaningful feedback from local resident actors, to ensure that the local community has an effective voice in decision-making processes for the development of public spaces. Third, more efforts are needed to disseminate the importance of the development and maintenance of public spaces and raise awareness among actors.

Our insights on how different governance actors can address the lack of coordination and mismanagement and the lack of social participation and dissemination of information can inform the formulation of policies on PSM for Mexican cities. As stated in other studies, information transparency in government institutions promotes efficiency and coordination, among other organisational values, and deepens the communication channels between government institutions and social actors (Brynskov et al., 2014; McCall & Dunn, 2012).

This study observed similar challenges to those encountered in

European contexts, particularly in enhancing participatory processes, as mentioned in the Dutch context (Duijvenvoorden et al., 2021). Given the lack of other PSM studies in non-European countries, this research makes an important empirical contribution to the scientific body of knowledge on PSM. We discuss the Mexican case study in a conceptual framework that allows placing the discussion in a wider Latin American context. We confirm existing challenges and highlight context-specific issues such as the proliferation of the informal sector, the ambiguity of laws and regulations, the lack of social participation and financial means to maintain public spaces. Our findings will be particularly helpful in Latin American cities with similar conditions or arrangements, such as Bogota in Colombia or Lima in Peru, where further studies are needed to expand the notion of PSM in an international discourse (ONU Habitat & CAF, 2014). Our conceptual framework operationalises the context of public spaces into the definition of a public space, the aspirations perceived to improve public spaces, and the conditions and functions perceived in public spaces; it includes social participation as an explicit and crucial dimension of the PSM framework. We conclude that the adjusted framework is a meaningful methodological device to guide our data analysis.

Future research and policy practice could explore innovative methods to involve residents in the planning, design and maintenance of public spaces. For example, Iran, Cyprus and the Netherlands are using Information and Communication Technology (ICTs) tools to improve social participation in PSM and support collaborative planning, design and maintenance (Artopoulos et al., 2019; Brynskov et al., 2014; Jelokhani-Niaraki et al., 2019). This is similar to what is happening in the emerging field of urban interaction design, where ICTs can be used to visualise possible public space scenarios, communicate among different stakeholders, or support the management of public spaces (Brynskov et al., 2014). For instance, the Management of Public Space Groningen (BORG)¹¹ helped the city of Groningen in the Netherlands to visualise and record the conditions of public spaces and evaluate management policies (Carmona et al., 2008); or the notification public space system (MOR)¹² in Amsterdam that allows residents to report issues with public spaces directly to the city. Findings point to the lack of conditions for social participation in PDMPs in Mexico, even though there are regulatory frameworks in place to support it, and practitioners recognise the value of including local residents in the process. Follow-up research will include the participation of local residents to understand how the development of public spaces is being developed from their perspective. In daily practice, digital participatory tools have the potential to facilitate the earlier involvement of local residents and other stakeholders in the planning, design, and maintenance of public spaces (Falco & Kleinhans, 2018; White et al., 2021). Using a digital participatory tool could enable the collection of valuable insights based on the needs and aspirations of local residents and create discussion with decision-makers, thereby facilitating the improvement of the quality of public spaces. This will also be the focus of follow-up research of our larger project.

One limitation of the research was the change of the Federal Government in Mexico in the period 2018–2024 which caused a change in the structure of some government agencies, complicating the search for the responsible authorities or actors for issues related to public space in Mexico. This may have caused the omission of certain perspectives in this research of which we are not aware. Another limitation concerns the validity of findings for the definition of what a public space is in the Mexican context. Since our interviewees mixed different scales and typologies when giving their definitions, findings on the definition could not be detailed with regard to scale and types of public spaces.

¹¹ The Dutch term is Beheer Openbare Ruimte Groningen.

¹² The Dutch term is Melding Openbare Ruimte en overlust.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sergio Alvarado Vazquez: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Ana Mafalda Madureira:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Frank O. Ostermann:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Karin Pfeffer:** Conceptualization, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Appendix A

Table 3

Documents obtained prior and after the interviews.

Documents obtained prior to the interviews	Documents provided by the interviewees
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constitution of Mexico of 1918 • National Plan of the Federal Administration 2013–2018 • National Plan of the Federal Administration 2019–2024 • Federal Law of Human Settlements, Territorial Order, and Urban Development (2016) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The State Development Plan of Puebla • Internal Law of the Ministry of Urban Mobility of the Municipality of Puebla (2017) • Law of Urban Development of Mexico City (2017) • Municipal plan of development of Puebla 2018–2021 • Operability Rules of the Federal Program of the Urban Improvement Program (period 2019) • Administrative manual of the Authority of Public Space of Mexico City (2017)

Table 4

Actors interviewed during fieldwork in Mexico.

City	Institutions	Group of actors	Date of the interview
Puebla City	Ministry of Mobility of Puebla	Local Government	13/11/2019
	Municipal Planning Institute of Puebla	Local Government	14/11/2019
	Mayor of the Romero Vargas district	Local Government	20/11/2019
	Authority of the Historic Center of Puebla	Local Government	21/01/2020
	Instituto de Ciencias Sociales Y Humanidades of the Autonomous University of Puebla (BUAP)	Academic	11/11/2019
	Faculty of Architecture of the Autonomous University of Puebla (BUAP)	Academic	14/11/2019
	College of planners and environmental designers of the state of Puebla.	NGO	14/11/2019
	Re-Genera Espacio	NGO	15/11/2019
	Entorno Paisaje	Architecture/urban planning firms	21/11/2019
	Ministry of Works and public services and former collaborators of the abolished Authority of Public Space	Local Government	30/11/2019
Mexico City	Ministry of Mobility of Mexico City and former collaborators of the abolished Authority of Public Space	Local Government	29/11/2019
	Metropolitan Autonomous University, Landscape program	Academic	18/11/2019
	The National University of Mexico,	Academic	26/11/2019
	Taller de Inovacion Urbana	NGO	28/11/2019
	Barriopolis	NGO	08/11/2019
	Thorsten Architects	Architecture/urban planning firms	09/11/2019
	Ministry of Agrarian, Territorial and Urban Development (SEDATU)	Federal Government	19/11/2019
Ministry of Agrarian, Territorial and Urban Development (SEDATU)	Federal Government	22/01/2020	
Ministry of Agrarian, Territorial and Urban Development (SEDATU)	Federal Government	23/01/2020	

Fig. 11. Codes obtained through the analysis of the regulatory documents prior the interviews using Atlas.ti software.

Fig. 12. Summary of findings of the PSM Framework in Mexico.

Table 6
Example of the digitalized data from the conducted interviews in Mexico.

Questions	NGO	Private sector	Academic
Sub-research question to be solved	Barriopolis	Thorsten Architects	Instituto de Ciencias Sociales Y Humanidades of the Autonomous University of Puebla (BUAP)
1.1. What is the definition of public space according to academics, NGOs and government actors in the Mexican context?	It is the place where the community converges. It is the basic space of the country with national importance, where it is undertaken and where everyone sees the others. It is the space where social understanding is	All the places in a city that are not private. They have a public function and involve complex multifunctionality. It can be economic or social. The public space needs to remain public and relate to private spaces. It needs to be an exchange of ideas.	A public space is a common good regulated by administrative laws. The public spaces are part of the city's production and are a basic element that belongs to everyone.

(continued on next page)

Table 6 (continued)

Questions	NGO	Private sector	Academic
	currently being lost, and public space is the mediator between the rural and the urban.	A shopping mall is private, and you can also have similar interactions in a private place. The difference is that you don't have an obligation to consume something, and it is accessible for everyone.	
2. For you, what is the importance of a public space in the city?	Public space is a basic element and very important in the city. It is important to be respected. Public space seeks to absorb aggressive urban sprawl in cities and helps build resilience for cities. It encourages people to go out and experience the city. It is a necessity for the city. Today's public spaces are being ignored in ferocious areas. The reality is different. There are no people in public spaces. Public space needs to be respected and regenerated, and it is the solution to fight against insecurity in the streets. The public space to invite people to go out and the space for transcendence in cities are strategic. We need inspiring public spaces.	It is very important. It is a public space where there is a social. Cultural and multifunctional exchange of interactions. The difference between the shopping mall is that it is private.	It is a fundamental element in the city. It is the space of the human conditions. It is a space where citizens generate public functions.

Fig. 13. Relevant literature identified in the Scopus database with the use of ASReview (20 out of 121 analysed records).

Storyboard for interviewing government workers

1.1 What is the definition of public space and its importance according to academics, NGOs and government actors in the Mexican context?

1. Can you explain what is a public space for you?
 ESPACIO NO EXCLUYE S DE LIBRE ACCESO, MULTIFUNCIÓN Y CON ACTIVIDADES
 AL AIRE LIBRE. NO TODOS CUMPLEN LA FUNCIÓN COMO LAS VIVIENDAS. Y HAY USO
 INEQUITATIVO

Urban designers and architects such as Gehl, Madanipour or Lucio reffer to public spaces as the open space where the city life unfolds and people interact, in places such as: streets, alleys, public squares, gardens, plazas or other open spaces that are considered part of the built environment(Gehl, 2004; Lucio, 2000; Madanipour, 2015).

2. For you, what is the importance of a public space in the city?
 FUNDAMENTAL, ES LO QUE ESTRUCTURA LA SOCIEDAD. ES LO QUE NO
 PERMITE VERNOS EN LO COLECTIVO.

3. Can you mention, according to you, the characteristics of an attractive public space?
 • TEMAS DE OJHA - (UNO DE PROPIA DEL ESPACIO SOMBRA)
 • ESPACIO INCLUSIVO - VERDE - ATRACTIVO - DISEÑO - DISEÑO ELEMENTO
 FUNDAMENTAL "VALOR ESTÉTICO"

1.2 What are the uses and functions of public spaces, according to the federal to local government agencies, academics, and NGOs in the Mexican context?

Public spaces have different functions, some researchers define that public spaces can have a social function, as spaces for encounters with friends and neighbors (Borja & Muxi, 2003; Harvey, 2000). Other persons explain that they can have a cultural function, such as places where people can express traditional habits or can function for religious purposes as well (Hinojosa & Moreno, 2016). Or even they have a spatial function, such as places for transition where flows of people, goods, and services interconnect and communicate with other parts of the city (Kray et al., 2013; Portal, 2016).

4. Can you explain what are the functions for which public spaces are currently planned and developed in the city (Puebla/Mexico)?
 • FUNCIÓN ECONOMICA - LAS CONDICIONES GENERICAS DE LA PRODUCCION.
 • COMO VISION ECONOMICA Y DE INFRAESTRUCTURA. LA FUNCIÓN SOCIAL PUEDE NOS
 ENCONTRAMOS, UN COLECTIVO, UNA VISION SOCIAL // O PARTE POLITICA. HACIA DONDE VANOS A LAS DIFERENTES
 ESCALAS ESTATAI, METROPOLITANO, COMO PROTESTAS. - SOCIEDAD => POLITICA PUBLICA -
 a. Did you know any regulation or normativity that mention the functions that a public space
 needs to have, or according to what/who are designed?
 • SI, HAY EN LA CONSTITUCION ART. 115 - NORMA OFICIAL MEXICANA DE E.P. A NIVEL SEDATU
 - DANDO COHERENCIA TERRITORIAL - TIENE UN ELEMENTO QUE PERMITE ASEGURAR SE TOMEN EN CUENTA
 - PARA PARA VIVIENDAS - SEPARADA DE E.P. - PERO SE CONSIDERA COMO E.P. PARA ELEGI
 - DESDE ASIGNAR PERMISOS O ASIGNAR A UN PARQUE UN ESPACIO EN UN E.P. PERO
 LOS 3 FUNCIONES EN VIVIENDAS. MARCO NORMATIVO

Fig. 14. Storyboard guide for our conducted interviews and the notes made during the conducted fieldwork in Mexico.

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